

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Deviation from Faraday's Law in the Electrolysis of Water

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In a previous communication¹, attention has been drawn to the possibility of deviation from Faraday's law. Since the above finding does profound violence to a well-accepted idea, more critical experiments were done limiting the work to the electrolysis of 'conductivity' water only. The results confirm the break-down of Faraday's law in such systems and this is reported in the present communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

In our previous experiments¹, the reproducibility was rather poor and it was found to be mainly due to the progressive contamination of water by traces of impurities from the rubber stoppers in contact with the electrolyte. In the present series of experiments all-glass coulometric cells² (Fig. 1) were used to avoid such contamination. The experi-

mental procedure was the same as described in our previous note. Two (or more) cells after proper cleaning and steaming were filled with 'conductivity' water and 0.5 *N* potassium sulphate solution respectively. The cells were connected in series and a current of the order of one milliampere was passed through the cell. This was just about the maximum current that could be passed on applying the full mains voltage (230 volts). During the first twenty four hours or so the electrolytes were allowed to be saturated with the electrolytic gas. After thorough saturation the supernatant gas was then let out. A series of consecutive experiments were then done on the same sample of water for a number of days as described below. The electrolysis was interrupted after a day or so as soon as 10 to 20 ml of gas collected in the coulometer; the volumes of gas collected in each cell were then measured with the help of the levelling burette, the collected gas was let out and the current was again switched on for a new experiment. With one filling of the cell a number of consecutive experiments were done. The most striking observation was that the volume of gas which collected over conductivity water was barely 10 per cent of what collected over the potassium sulphate solution. To overcome any spurious factor the direction of the current was changed but the results were the same. The contents of the cells were then interchanged by draining out, cleaning and refilling, but the results were the same. Current was also drawn from lead accumulator instead of the mains and the same kind of results was obtained. So far over one hundred experiments were carried out in such all-glass cells and the results were consistently the same as mentioned

1. S. R. Palit, *Ind., J. Physics*, 1967, 41, 390.

2. K. Abresh and I. Clausen, *Coulometric Analysis*, (Translated by L. L. Leveson). Chapman and Hall, 1960, p. 80.

above. Though the volume of gas which collected over water was very much less than that expected from Faraday's law, the volume of gas collected in the coulometer was generally close to the theoretical value as long as the current was not much below the region of one milliampere.

Most of our experiments were done with current of the order of one milliampere; however, some experiments were also done at 25-microamperes. This confirmed our previous finding that electrolysis of water gave results in wide departure from Faraday's law. In fact with such low amperage hardly any gas collected over conductivity water in the course of a few days. Surprisingly, the volume of gas collected over the potassium sulphate solution was also considerably less than the theoretical value. These results indicate that Faraday's law tends to fail more and more as the current density is reduced. Some representative data are shown below.

Current	Duration (approx)	Volume gas collected in		Per cent Non-electrolytic conduction
		Coulometer cc.	Water cell c.c	
0.5 mA	2 days	17.2	0.7	4.1
	1 day	8.0	0.5	6.25
	"	9.0	0.6	6.7
	"	9.4	0.7	7.5
	"	8.8	0.6	6.8
1 mA	"	9.3	0.4	4.3
	1 day	17.0	1.5	8.8
	"	19.2	1.8	9.4
	"	21.3	1.9	8.9
25 μ A	5 days	0.8	less than 0.1 cc	
	10 days	1.7	"	

These results confirm our previous findings made with a not-so-precise set-up, and we reiterate our conclusion that Faraday's law breaks down in the electrolysis of conductivity water at least under our experimental conditions. Evidently, electrolytic conduction takes place in current conduction through water. As to the mechanism of the non-electrolytic conduction, the evident possibility is electronic conduction as occurs in some crystals and in solution of sodium in liquid ammonia where both electrolytic as well as electronic conduction simultaneously takes place. However, another possibility should not be lost sight of, viz., conduction by charged water molecules; $(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-_{aq}$ and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})^+_{aq}$. This is more likely to be so as the existence of hydrated electron during electrolysis has been lately demonstrated³. Further investigations are in progress.

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3. D. C. Walker, *Quarterly Reviews*, 1967, 21, 83; *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1966, 44, 2226.